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CONSUMER PROPERTIES OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UZBEKISTAN: TRADITIONS, TRANSFORMATION AND NEW QUALITY STANDARDS

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Abstract: This article examines the consumer properties of food products in Uzbekistan as a key factor shaping the national food model and the economic development of the industry. Based on data from Euromonitor International, official decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and materials from international organizations (FAO/WHO), the main characteristics of the food market are analyzed: traditional taste preferences, growing demand for value-added products, digitalization processes, and standardization. Special attention is paid to the transformation of approaches to food safety in the context of harmonization with international norms and the country's accession to the WTO.

Keywords: food products, consumer properties, Uzbekistan, food safety, standardization, processed products, export potential.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekistonda oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarining iste'mol xususiyatlari milliy oziq-ovqat modeli va tarmoqning iqtisodiy rivojlanishini shakllantiruvchi muhim omil sifatida o'rganilgan. Euromonitor International ma'lumotlari, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti farmon va qarorlari hamda xalqaro tashkilotlar (FAO/WHO) materiallari asosida oziq-ovqat bozorining asosiy xususiyatlari, jumladan, an'anaviy ta'm afzalliklari, qo'shilgan qiymatga ega mahsulotlarga talabning ortishi, raqamlashtirish jarayonlari va standartlashtirish masalalari tahlil qilingan. Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligiga yondashuvlarning xalqaro me'yorlar bilan uyg'unlashtirilishi va mamlakatning JSTga qo'shilishi sharoitida ushbu sohadagi o'zgarishlarga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari, iste'mol xususiyatlari, O'zbekiston, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, standartlashtirish, qayta ishlangan mahsulotlar, eksport salohiyati.

Аннотация: В данной статье потребительские свойства пищевых продуктов в Узбекистане рассматриваются как ключевой фактор формирования национальной продовольственной модели и экономического развития отрасли. На основе данных Euromonitor International, указов и постановлений Президента Республики Узбекистан, а также материалов международных организаций (FAO/WHO) проанализированы основные характеристики продовольственного рынка, включая традиционные вкусовые предпочтения, растущий спрос на продукцию с добавленной стоимостью, процессы цифровизации и стандартизации. Особое внимание уделено трансформации подходов к обеспечению безопасности пищевых продуктов в условиях гармонизации с международными нормами и вступления страны во Всемирную торговую организацию (ВТО).

Ключевые слова: пищевые продукты, потребительские свойства, Узбекистан, безопасность пищевых продуктов, стандартизация, переработанная продукция, экспортный потенциал.

INTRODUCTION

The consumer properties of food products are a set of qualitative characteristics that determine their ability to satisfy human nutritional needs. These include organoleptic indicators (taste, smell, color, consistency), nutritional value (content of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals), safety (absence of harmful impurities and pathogenic microorganisms), as well as attributes such as freshness, naturalness, and ease of preparation.

For Uzbekistan, which possesses rich agro-climatic resources and deep culinary traditions, understanding the consumer properties of food products is of particular importance. It underpins both domestic food policy and the strategy for increasing export potential. In a country where “affordability, familiarity, and taste remain the main drivers of consumer choice” (Cooking Ingredients and Meals in Uzbekistan., 2025.), the transformation of preferences under the influence of urbanization and changing lifestyles opens up new opportunities for producers and retailers. Producers, in turn, relying on traditional consumer preferences and their stability, acquire and manufacture products. One of the key features of consumer behavior in Uzbekistan is the strong preference for fresh, natural products. As analysts at Euromonitor International note, “a strong cultural preference for fresh products” continues to restrain demand for processed fruits and vegetables, despite growing urbanization (Processed Fruit and Vegetables in Uzbekistan., 2025.).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Food products occupy a strategic position in ensuring food security, improving public health, and enhancing the competitiveness of national economies. The consumer properties of food products have therefore become an important subject of research in economics, food science, marketing, and consumer behavior studies. Scientific literature demonstrates that consumer evaluation of food products is shaped by a combination of sensory attributes, nutritional value, safety indicators, convenience, and socio-cultural factors.

One of the most influential contributions to the understanding of food quality was made by Jean-Claude Caswell, who emphasized that food quality should be viewed as a multidimensional concept encompassing nutritional characteristics, food safety, product composition, and consumer perceptions. Caswell argued that modern food markets increasingly rely on information systems and quality assurance mechanisms to reduce information asymmetry between producers and consumers. Her research highlighted the growing importance of certification and labeling systems in shaping consumer trust.

The relationship between food quality and consumer preferences has also been extensively examined by W. Fred van Raaij. His studies demonstrated that consumer food choices are influenced not only by objective product characteristics but also by psychological, social, and cultural determinants. According to van Raaij, purchasing behavior in food markets is closely connected with lifestyle patterns, household income levels, and cultural traditions. These findings are particularly relevant for countries with strong culinary traditions, where consumer preferences remain relatively stable over long periods.

Research conducted by Klaus Grunert significantly expanded the understanding of consumer perceptions of food quality. Grunert emphasized that consumers often evaluate food products through a combination of intrinsic attributes such as taste, freshness, color, and texture, as well as extrinsic attributes including brand reputation, country of origin, packaging, and certification. His studies revealed that trust plays a central role in consumer acceptance of food products, particularly in markets characterized by increasing product differentiation and globalization.

The issue of food safety has received considerable attention in the works of Marion Nestle. She examined the interaction between food systems, public health, and regulatory institutions. Nestle argued that food safety standards and government oversight mechanisms are essential for protecting consumers and maintaining confidence in food markets. Her findings indicate that food quality and safety should not be viewed separately because consumers increasingly associate product quality with safety assurance and transparency throughout the supply chain.

The growing importance of international food standards has been explored by Tim Josling. His research demonstrated that harmonization of food regulations with international frameworks such as Codex Alimentarius facilitates international trade while simultaneously improving consumer protection. Josling emphasized that compliance with internationally recognized standards enhances export opportunities and strengthens the competitiveness of domestic producers in global markets.

Consumer attitudes toward food labeling and certification have been widely studied by David Byrne and colleagues within the context of European food markets. Their findings indicate that quality labels, origin certifications, and safety assurances significantly influence purchasing decisions. The researchers concluded that transparent information systems contribute to higher levels of consumer confidence and create incentives for producers to improve product quality.

The relationship between urbanization and changing food consumption patterns has been investigated by Barry Popkin. His studies on nutrition transition demonstrated that economic development and urban growth lead to significant transformations in consumer preferences. As household incomes rise and lifestyles become more dynamic, consumers tend to increase demand for convenience foods, ready-to-eat products,

and processed food items. Nevertheless, traditional food preferences often remain influential, especially in developing countries with strong cultural food identities.

Recent studies conducted by the Food and Agriculture Organization and the World Health Organization emphasize that food quality management systems based on HACCP principles and Codex Alimentarius standards have become critical tools for ensuring food safety and enhancing export competitiveness. These organizations highlight that modern food systems require integrated approaches that combine quality assurance, traceability, sustainability, and consumer protection.

Overall, the existing literature demonstrates that the consumer properties of food products are determined by a complex interaction of sensory quality, nutritional value, food safety, cultural traditions, consumer trust, and regulatory frameworks. Contemporary research increasingly emphasizes the importance of harmonizing national food standards with international requirements while preserving the traditional preferences and cultural characteristics of local consumers. These theoretical approaches provide an important foundation for analyzing the transformation of consumer properties of food products in Uzbekistan under conditions of urbanization, market modernization, and export-oriented development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on secondary data obtained from reports of Euromonitor International, publications of the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the World Health Organization (WHO), official legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and statistical materials related to the food sector. The collected information was analyzed using comparative, descriptive, and logical analysis methods to identify trends in consumer preferences, food quality characteristics, safety standards, and the development of the food market in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This trend is most evident in the market for sweet spreads (jams, marmalades, preserves, confitures). The Euromonitor analytical report for 2024 records stagnation in this category, as “local consumers continue to prefer fresh fruit over canned jams and spreads” (Uzbekistan Market Research., 2025.). Traditional flavors (apricot, quince, fig) remain dominant, and it is difficult for manufacturers to introduce innovative offerings.

A similar picture is observed in the processed fruit and vegetable segment as a whole. According to Euromonitor International data from December 2025, this category “shows the weakest growth among the main food categories,” which is explained by the wide availability and affordable price of fresh products (Uzbekistan Market Research., 2025.). Nevertheless, differentiation exists within this segment: canned beans show the most dynamic growth in value terms, and frozen vegetables in volume terms, indicating the gradual penetration of convenience factors (Uzbekistan Market Research., 2025.).

The influence of traditions is also evident in the vegetable oils market. Euromonitor analysts note that “traditional culinary habits continue to support steady growth” in this segment, with consumers switching to sunflower oil as a healthier alternative to other types of fats (Cooking Ingredients and Meals in Uzbekistan., 2025.). Against this backdrop, the influence of urbanization on the transformation of consumer properties is significant; urbanization and changing lifestyles are becoming powerful drivers of change. According to Euromonitor International data for 2025, “the market for cooking ingredients and ready meals in Uzbekistan continues to expand, driven by rising urbanization and more hectic lifestyles, increasing demand for convenient and semi-prepared solutions” (Cooking Ingredients and Meals in Uzbekistan., 2025.).

This trend is particularly evident in the ready meals and soups segment. The Euromonitor 2024 report emphasizes that “the ready meals and soups market in Uzbekistan is experiencing substantial growth, with a noticeable increase in both the number of market players and the variety of products available compared to previous years” [9]. This growth is supported by increased ownership of freezers among urban households, which stimulates demand for frozen ready meals (Cooking Ingredients and Meals in Uzbekistan., 2025.).

At the same time, analysts note that “healthy eating and wellness trends are still having a limited impact on the ready meals and soups market” (Cooking Ingredients and Meals in Uzbekistan., 2025.). For the Uzbek consumer, taste and familiarity remain paramount, which is also confirmed in other categories: in the sauces, dressings, and condiments segment, “taste and value for money are more important than health benefits” (Cooking Ingredients and Meals in Uzbekistan., 2025.).

A growing interest in culinary experimentation is becoming an important trend. According to Euromonitor International 2025 data, “Uzbek consumers are increasingly experimenting with new flavors” (Cooking Ingredients and Meals in Uzbekistan., 2025.). This creates opportunities to expand the range of sauces, seasonings, and

ready-made condiments, including a wider variety of international flavors. Uzbekistan is increasingly producing export-oriented goods, which give an export vector and create added value while defining international quality standards for manufactured products. In this regard, the consumer properties of food products are of particular importance in the context of Uzbekistan's export strategy. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. RP-136¹ of April 8, 2025 "On additional measures to increase the export potential of agricultural products and to develop the processing chain", sets ambitious target indicators: "increasing the total export volume of fruit, vegetable, and food products to 3.5 billion US dollars in 2025" (M) (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan., 2025., Tax benefits granted to certain., 2025.). By 2027, this benchmark rises to 4 billion US dollars (Uzbekistan plans to increase food., 2025.).

A key mechanism for achieving these indicators is the creation of a value-added chain through the development of processing and modern packaging. The state encourages these processes with tax incentives: for entrepreneurs selling fruit and vegetable products in modern packaging who comply with certain conditions (paying wages of at least twice the minimum wage, with the share of packaged products at least 50% of total income), "corporate income tax and social tax rates are set at 1 percent" until January 1, 2028 (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan., 2025.).

Furthermore, in 2025–2026, agricultural cooperatives that collect, sort, and sell fruit and vegetable products in modern packaging will receive "reimbursement of 25% of packaging costs, but not exceeding three thousand soums per package" (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan., 2025.). Cooperative members must undergo training through the "Edukarantin.uz" information system and obtain the appropriate certificate, after which a rating system in the categories "green," "yellow," and "red" is assigned (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan., 2025.).

The development of storage infrastructure is also a priority. Decree PP-136 allows agricultural enterprises with a land area of at least 5 hectares "to build cold storage facilities, sorting, drying, processing, and packaging technologies on 1% of the total land area, but not exceeding 20 acres" (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan., 2025.). This directly affects the consumer properties of exported products – preserving freshness, extending shelf life, and improving appearance. To this end, Uzbekistan is integrating into the international system of standardization and food safety. In turn, the consumer properties of food products cannot be considered separately from the system of standardization and safety control. In Uzbekistan, a radical reform is underway in this area aimed at harmonization with international norms.

On April 18, 2025, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a decree № DP-67² "On measures to stimulate production, export and entrepreneurial activities, and improve the effectiveness of trade and industrial policy", according to which, from August 1, 2025, "technical regulations and standards for food products lose their mandatory force. Instead, sanitary rules, norms, and hygienic standards (SanPiN), developed by the committee and agreed upon with relevant agencies, will be in effect" (SanPiN instead of standards., 2025.). Food safety control is fully transferred to the Committee for Sanitary and Epidemiological Welfare and Public Health (SanPiN instead of standards., 2025.).

The new SanPiN No. 0079-24, approved on November 14, 2024, and effective from June 17, 2025, establishes maximum permissible levels of contaminants, pesticide residue limits and veterinary drug residues, microbiological criteria, and rules for the use of food additives (Resolution of the Committee for Sanitary., 2025., Seminar on harmonizing Uzbekistan's food safety., 2025.).

Harmonization with the international Codex Alimentarius standard is a crucial step. As the head of state noted at a meeting with entrepreneurs, the committee must adapt SanPiN for the main types of food products to international requirements, including the Codex Alimentarius, within three months (SanPiN instead of standards., 2025.). As part of the FAO/WHO project "Strengthening national capacity for the sustainable functioning of Codex Alimentarius in Uzbekistan," a seminar was held in September 2025 to discuss steps to bring national legislation into line with international standards (Seminar on harmonizing Uzbekistan's food safety., 2025.). On August 5, 2025, a new "Food Safety Law" was adopted (Seminar on harmonizing Uzbekistan's food safety., 2025.).

These transformations open up new opportunities for Uzbek exporters. As noted by Shukhrat Ergashev, founder of International Beverages Tashkent, at a meeting with the president, "the transition to the Codex Alimentarius will stimulate the export of local producers" (SanPiN instead of standards., 2025.).

At the Tashkent State Agrarian University, training seminars are being held for teachers, doctoral students, and students on the requirements of the international standard ISO 22000, the HACCP system, as well as Codex Alimentarius food safety standards (Discussed innovations in food safety and standardization., 2026.). This contributes to building human capacity for implementing modern quality standards.

1 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/7472477>

2 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/7485039>

In Uzbekistan, increasing importance is being attached to new formats and distribution channels as a factor in changing consumer properties, which leads to changes in retail trade. In turn, the transformation of retail trade also affects consumer perceptions of food product properties. According to Euromonitor International, “small local grocery stores remain the dominant distribution channel” for basic food products (Uzbekistan Market Research., 2025.). However, e-commerce is showing impressive growth rates: “the e-commerce channel is registering the fastest growth in value sales volume” (Uzbekistan Market Research., 2025.).

Large modern retailers are strengthening their positions through the development of private labels, especially in the vegetable oils segment (Cooking Ingredients and Meals in Uzbekistan., 2025.). This expands consumer choice and creates a competitive environment that stimulates quality improvement.

The “E-logistika” platform is designed to ensure direct interaction between exporting enterprises and carriers, which should reduce delivery times and improve product safety during transportation (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan., 2025.). This will help products manufactured both in Uzbekistan and abroad avoid major trade fluctuations. Furthermore, the consumer properties of food products in Uzbekistan are at a crossroads: traditions remain strongly influential, but urbanization and changing lifestyles are gradually transforming demand. Key trends in the coming years include:

1. *Growing demand for convenient formats.* Euromonitor predicts that «the convenience factor will continue to drive consumption» of processed fruits and vegetables (Uzbekistan Market Research., 2025.). However, the pace of this growth will be constrained by strong adherence to fresh products.

2. *Limited influence of health as a selection criterion.* In the foreseeable future, «affordability, familiarity, and taste will remain the main drivers of consumer choice». Healthy eating trends will influence the market mainly through online channels and in the specialized products segment (Cooking Ingredients and Meals in Uzbekistan., 2025.).

3. *Expansion of assortment and culinary experiments.* The growing availability of international products and interest in new flavors will contribute to the diversification of offerings in the sauces, seasonings, and ready meals categories.

4. *“Halal” certification as a factor of trust.* Euromonitor notes that «halal certification will remain central to consumer trust» in the ready meals and soups segment (Cooking Ingredients and Meals in Uzbekistan., 2025.).

5. *Harmonization of standards with international norms.* Uzbekistan’s accession to the WTO and the adaptation of SanPiN to Codex Alimentarius requirements will create the basis for recognition of Uzbek products in foreign markets.

This, in turn, demonstrates the commitment of Uzbek citizens to high-quality food products based on consumer preferences, which will fully meet international requirements.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The consumer properties of food products in Uzbekistan are formed at the intersection of deep culinary traditions and modern urbanization trends. The strong preference for fresh, natural products, the love of traditional flavors, and loyalty to familiar formats remain key characteristics of the domestic market. However, increasing urbanization and changing lifestyles are gradually transforming demand towards more convenient formats – frozen semi-finished products, ready meals, and various sauces.

The country’s export strategy directs the industry towards creating added value through the development of processing, modern packaging, and storage infrastructure. State support for these processes through tax incentives and subsidies creates incentives for producers.

The systemic reform of food standardization and safety, the transition to SanPiN harmonized with Codex Alimentarius, and the implementation of international quality management systems (ISO 22000, HACCP) lay the foundation for increasing confidence in Uzbek products both in domestic and foreign markets.

Thus, the consumer properties of food products in Uzbekistan are a dynamically developing category, reflecting both the preservation of cultural identity and adaptation to the contemporary challenges of the global food market. The successful combination of traditions and innovations, backed by institutional reforms, will allow the country not only to ensure food security but also to occupy a worthy place in the international arena.

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